

Usefulness of the Alvarado Scale in Patients with Suspected Acute Appendicitis in Relation to Imaging Results

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ABSTRACT

Background: Multiple studies demonstrate that the Alvarado Score is less effective than other studies in predicting the incidence of patients with suspected acute appendicitis. It does not distinguish between ages and does not suggest a clinical stage of the disease. However, its use is still current in our unit and in most hospitals in our country.

General Objective: To identify the utility of the Alvarado Score in patients with suspected acute appendicitis in relation to imaging results.

Materials and Methods: Descriptive, observational, cross-sectional, retrospective study, which was carried out with 62 records of patients with suspected acute appendicitis and who were requested imaging studies at the Regional General Hospital 1 of Orizaba, Veracruz with the suspected diagnosis of Acute Appendicitis during the period from December 1, 2017 to November 30, 2022. Patients of any age group and both sexes who came to the emergency service with pain in the right iliac fossa and classified with the Alvarado scale that met the selection criteria were included. This study was conducted from March 1 to September 30, 2023. Data analysis included descriptive statistics for qualitative variables using frequencies and percentages, as well as measures of dispersion. For quantitative variables, such as mean and standard deviation, the Fisher exact test was used between variables with two categories based on the nature of the categorical variables. SPSS 23 and GraphPad Prism 8 software were used.

Resources and infrastructure: those of the institution, the patients, and the researcher.

Group experience: There is a master's degree in science and a radiologist with experience in ultrasound and CT interpretation. A resident physician who will carry out the activities of the research project.

Results: The female sex predominated with a frequency of 40 patients (56.33%) with a mean age of 28.80 years, standard deviation +/- 19.36 (95% CI 22.61-34.99), of the male sex a frequency of 31 patients (43.66%) was observed with a mean age of 28.16 years, standard deviation +/- 17.69, the time of onset of symptoms: 35 patients (49.3%) began with symptoms at 24 hours, followed by 15 patients (21.1%) at 12 hours, 11 patients (15.5%) at 72 hours, 7 patients reported onset of symptoms at 48 hours (9.9%). The relationship between the Alvarado scale and imaging studies was identified using Fisher's exact test. The P value was 0.8791, which is considered statistically insignificant.

Conclusion: The Alvarado score has proven to be a useful, simple, noninvasive, and rapid tool for guiding the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. However, due to its low specificity, the use of imaging studies is always recommended to confirm suspected diagnoses.

KEYWORDS: Score, Alvarado, utility, tomography, ultrasound

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INTRODUCTION

Acute appendicitis is defined as inflammation of the vermiform appendix, when there is obstruction resulting in an inflammatory response that leads to vascular compromise and progresses to perforation, culminating in complications such as localized abscesses or generalized peritonitis. Its frequency is 50 per 100,000 inhabitants with a peak incidence between the ages of 10 and 30 years.¹

To achieve a timely and accurate diagnosis, various scoring systems have been developed, such as the Alvarado scale, one of the most recognized worldwide, with a sensitivity of 68% and a specificity of 89.96%. This scale considers symptoms, vital signs, and laboratory studies. However, it has been shown that this scale is insufficient to establish a presumptive diagnosis or rule it out; therefore, confirmation through imaging studies is crucial.⁷

Contrast-enhanced computed tomography is the imaging study with the highest sensitivity and specificity for the diagnosis of appendicitis and allows for the detection of gangrene, perforation, or peri-appendiceal abscess. Another study frequently used in clinical practice is ultrasound, considered the first line of diagnosis for suspected appendicitis in children. This instrument is less sensitive and specific but has the advantage of being more economical and more readily available in hospital units.

Currently, there is no local validation of the Alvarado scale in relation to available imaging studies such as ultrasound and computed tomography, making it essential to understand in detail the usefulness of this predictive scale.¹⁵

FRAMEWORK

One of the most common causes of acute abdomen, acute appendicitis is a staple of any general surgeon's practice. Despite recent advances in the management of acute appendicitis, considerable controversy has arisen regarding diagnostic algorithms and potential differential diagnoses, leading to a lack of absolute consensus in the literature. It is characterized by inflammation of the vermiform appendix, occurring when there is obstruction of the appendiceal orifice, resulting in inflammation. This causes progressive distension of the appendix, eventually leading to vascular compromise, which allows for the growth of pathogenic microorganisms. If left untreated, it culminates in perforation of the appendix with a localized abscess or generalized peritonitis. Therefore, surgeons must maintain a low threshold for surgery to minimize the rate of complications. No time should be wasted ordering additional investigations if they will not significantly alter the management plan. The classic sequence of periumbilical pain radiating to the right iliac fossa (RIF), nausea or vomiting, and fever raises suspicion of appendicitis. Many clinical signs are described, such as Blumberg's sign (rebound tenderness), Rovsing's sign (pain in the right iliac fossa when palpating the left iliac fossa) or

the psoas sign (pain when flexing the right hip that suggests retrocecal appendicitis)^{1,2}

In developed countries, acute appendicitis occurs in 5.7–50 patients per 100,000 inhabitants per year, with a peak between the ages of 10 and 30. The perforation rate varies from 16% to 40%, with a higher frequency in younger age groups (40–50%) and in patients over 50 years of age (55–70%). Appendiceal perforation is associated with increased morbidity and mortality compared to non-perforated acute appendicitis. The mortality risk for non-gangrenous acute appendicitis is less than 0.1%, but this risk rises to 0.6% in gangrenous acute appendicitis. Perforated acute appendicitis, on the other hand, carries an increased mortality rate of approximately 5%.³

The higher proportion of preschool children presenting with acute appendicitis (13.4% compared to 2–9% in other studies) may have sensitized healthcare workers to acute appendicitis as a differential diagnosis, thus reducing delays in referral and subsequent treatment. Histological review revealed a normal appendix in 8.4% of patients. The percentage of negative appendectomies was higher in patients under 6 years of age (11.4%), highlighting the diagnostic difficulty in this age group, where patients present with signs and symptoms suggestive of acute appendicitis, only to have the diagnosis ruled out at the time of surgery.⁴

Patients with appendicitis but normal inflammatory markers had less frequent pain migration. Other symptoms, such as vomiting (34.4%) and localized (86.6%) or diffuse (9.7%) peritonitis, were not significantly different compared to those with elevated inflammatory parameters. Atema et al. showed a negative predictive value (NPV) of up to 90% for normal inflammatory parameters in acute appendicitis, regardless of symptom duration, within a 5-day range. Therefore, they concluded that normal inflammatory markers cannot sufficiently exclude a suspected diagnosis of acute appendicitis within this 5-day range.

Children with appendicitis appear to have a distinct metabolomic and inflammatory profile. This biomarker pattern provides insights into the underlying pathophysiological processes of the disease and has the potential to be used to develop a clinical tool to aid in the diagnosis of pediatric appendicitis. Other future directions could include biomarker phenotyping for stratifying children with appendicitis according to disease severity (simple versus perforated).⁶

The importance of timely and accurate diagnosis has led researchers to develop different scoring systems. The Alvarado score is the first and most widely used among them. Subraman et al. reported that the sensitivity and specificity of the Alvarado score were 68% and 86.96%, respectively. Elhosseiny et al. found these values to be 65.2% and 100%, respectively. Khan et al. reported negative appendicitis and perforated appendectomy rates of 15.6% and 7.8%, respectively.

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The Alvarado score considers symptoms, signs, and laboratory results. ([Appendix III](#)) Some studies have shown that the diagnostic accuracy of the Alvarado score is insufficient to establish a presumptive diagnosis or rule it out, especially in children, and this can lead to delays in diagnosis and increase the risk of appendicitis perforation. Other studies demonstrate that combining the Alvarado score with C-Reactive Protein is a useful diagnostic tool for ruling out acute appendicitis in patients aged 2 to 20 years presenting with abdominal pain suggestive of acute appendicitis. This strategy showed an improvement in the diagnostic accuracy of the Alvarado score compared to when used alone. Predictive models have been sought that could identify children at high risk of complicated appendicitis better than the Alvarado score and others such as the PAS (Pediatric Appendicitis Screening Test). Appendicitis Score). This model could be used to help differentiate between simple and complicated acute appendicitis for optimal treatment strategy.^{8,9}

A study examined the relationship between patients operated on for a diagnosis of acute appendicitis who had a histopathology result and the Alvarado score. The sensitivity and specificity of the Alvarado score at cutoff points of 5 and 7 were assessed. We found that the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were 91.20%, 22.64%, 96.5%, and 9.8%, respectively, at a cutoff point of 5, and the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV were 66.40%, 69.81%, 98.1%, and 8.1%, respectively, at a cutoff point of 7.¹⁰

Recent studies have shown approximately similar results. Pifeleti et al. reported that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV with an Alvarado score ≥ 5 were 91.97%, 50%, 98.44%, and 15.38%, respectively, and with an Alvarado score ≥ 7 were 63.5%, 75%, 98.86%, and 5.66%, respectively. Furthermore, Nascimento et al. It demonstrated a sensitivity of 88.17%, specificity of 37.5%, PPV of 94.25%, and NPV of 21.43% for an Alvarado score ≥ 5 , and a sensitivity of 38.71%, specificity of 87.5%, PPV of 97.3%, and NPV of 10.94% for an Alvarado score ≥ 7 . It was noted that with increasing cutoff points, sensitivity decreased, but specificity increased. Another study validated the Alvarado score at a cutoff value ≥ 7 and reported a lower sensitivity of 54%, specificity of 75%, PPV of 90%, and NPV of 29%, concluding that the Alvarado score was not a useful method in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis.¹⁰

Specifically, these tools (PAS and Alvarado) generally place most patients in intermediate-risk categories, indicating the need for imaging. This contrasts with the pARC (Pediatric Appendicitis Risk Calculator), in which most patients are classified into low- and high-risk categories, which could help mitigate the use of imaging. Pediatric patients presenting with acute abdominal pain would have been assigned a low-risk pARC score, allowing the clinician to defer diagnostic imaging. Furthermore, in the subgroup assigned an intermediate pARC score, the high rate of equivocal

ultrasound readings and the low ultimate risk of appendicitis suggest that these patients can be managed with observation rather than ultrasound. Finally, among patients with pARC scores $\geq 85\%$ (high), it would be reasonable and safe to encourage surgical evaluation with the selective use of diagnostic imaging. Data presented in another study suggest that widespread use of point-of-care pARC scoring could facilitate a reduction in the use of ultrasound (USG), computed tomography (CT), and magnetic resonance imaging.^{11,12}

Lack of agreement with the recommendations, coupled with system-level barriers, may result in limited compliance. For patients at low to moderate risk (i.e., pARC score of 16 % to 25%), the CDS (Clinical Decision Support System) recommends observation before imaging, but this may not be practical in busy emergency departments with limited space for pediatric patients. For many community-based emergency departments, the CDS recommendations resulted in a lack of implementation of care (i.e., foregoing ultrasound in patients at low risk for appendicitis).¹³</sup>

Clinical scores alone, such as Alvarado, Appendicitis Inflammatory Response (AIR) and the new Adult The Appendicitis Score (AAS) appears sensitive enough to exclude acute appendicitis, accurately identify low-risk patients, and decrease the need for negative imaging studies and surgical explorations (as well as diagnostic laparoscopy) in patients with suspected acute appendicitis. Patients with strong signs and symptoms and a high risk of appendicitis according to the AIR/Alvarado/AAS score, and who are younger than 40 years of age, are unlikely to require preoperative imaging studies. Although the Alvarado score is not specific enough to diagnose acute appendicitis, a score cutoff of <5 is sensitive enough to exclude acute appendicitis (99% sensitivity). The Alvarado score can be used to decrease emergency department length of stay and radiation exposure in patients suspected of having acute appendicitis. Based on this evidence, laparoscopic abdominal exploration without imaging is recommended as an option in young patients with a high probability score for appendicitis.¹⁴

Although clinical appearance and scoring systems such as the Alvarado score are generally sufficient to exclude acute appendicitis, they have limited utility in discriminating between uncomplicated and complicated appendicitis. For this reason, this task relies heavily on contrast-enhanced CT (sensitivity and specificity of 92.6% and 96.9%, respectively), which can diagnose uncomplicated appendicitis when there is no evidence of gangrene, perforation, periappendiceal abscess, appendicolith, or suspected tumor. Similarly, in some studies, the Alvarado scoring system did not prove very useful in aiding the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in such settings, probably due to the heterogeneous patient population studied. Further refinements and adjustments may be needed to improve the sensitivity of the scoring system and reduce the controversy surrounding its routine use.^{15,16}

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Bhangu et al. studied multiple prediction models; of the 15 models (including the Alvarado scale), 11 showed consistently good discrimination for identifying appendicitis (AUC above 0.7) in both women and men. In women, the Adult The Appendicitis Score (AAS) achieved the highest specificity while maintaining a failure rate of less than 5% in low-risk patients. With a cutoff score of 8 or less, the AAS classified 63.1% of women without appendicitis into the low-risk group (specificity), and among all women in the low-risk group, 3.7% actually had appendicitis (failure rate). In men, the optimal model was Appendicitis Inflammatory Response Score (AIRS), with a cutoff score of 2 or less associated with a specificity of 24.7% and a failure rate of 2.4%.¹⁷

Atema and colleagues developed two scoring systems for predicting complicated or uncomplicated acute appendicitis, combining clinical and radiological features: one with ultrasonographic features and the other with CT. The ultrasonographic system achieved a sensitivity of 96.6% and a specificity of 45.7%; for CT, the sensitivity and specificity were 90.2% and 70.3%, respectively. Avanesov and colleagues developed a scoring system with CT features; the sensitivity was 82% and the specificity 93%. However, these scoring models have not yet been externally validated.¹⁸

Therefore, it has been believed that the clinical judgment of an experienced surgeon might be superior to the effectiveness of scoring systems in distinguishing (especially) children with suspected appendicitis. Even so, there is a demand to compare different scoring tools to facilitate the management process among younger patients.¹⁹

Overall, ultrasound is usually the first-line imaging modality for suspected appendicitis in children. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) for ultrasound were 82%, 97%, 92%, and 93%, respectively. Factors that might affect the variation in sensitivity are an area of interest. One study showed lower sensitivity in girls. Another factor is operator dependence. An equivocal result, when the appendix is only partially visualized or not visualized at all, is not uncommon when using ultrasound. The operator-dependent nature of ultrasound may possibly explain some of the discrepancy in sensitivity between ultrasound and CT. A higher rate of appendix identification in children has been shown to be related to hospital experience in the routine use of ultrasound and whether the ultrasound examiner has pediatric experience. Furthermore, a higher rate of appendix identification would likely increase the sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound for suspected appendicitis.²⁰

Ultrasound has recently been shown to be a reliable imaging method for differentiating between perforated and non-perforated appendicitis using highly specific techniques: appendiceal wall diameter > 6 mm (sensitivity 98%), periappendiceal fat edema (44%), free abdominal fluid (41%), abscess (2%), conglomerate (1%), appendicolith (13%), and lymphadenitis (16%). Appendiceal diameter is measured from outer wall to outer wall. Appendiceal wall

edema is defined as obliteration of the layers. Periappendiceal fat inflammation is diagnosed when increased echogenicity is observed in the periappendiceal tissue. Free abdominal fluid is defined as localized fluid, whether simple or complex, in or away from the appendix, while an abscess is diagnosed when an accumulation of periappendiceal fluid is identified. A conglomerate was defined as a grouped appendix or one indistinguishable from other intestinal structures. An appendicolith was diagnosed when an intraluminal hyperechoic focus with acoustic shadowing was identified. Lymphadenitis was defined as the sonographic detection of lymph nodes. In some cases, the radiologist documented a suspicion of perforation due to the overall composition of pathological changes.²¹

Neal et al. studied secondary ultrasound findings in a pediatric population according to age groups. Free fluid was most commonly seen, occurring in 63.4% of cases, while an appendicolith was less frequently observed, in 18.0% of cases. Echogenic fat had the highest test performance overall (sensitivity 94%, specificity 91%) and in all age groups. Free fluid had the lowest test performance overall (sensitivity 74%, specificity 43%) and in all age groups. The presence of an appendicolith was more predictive of appendicitis in the youngest age group (<6 years) compared to the middle-aged group (6 to <11 years) and the oldest group (11 to <19 years). Free fluid was more predictive of appendicitis in the middle-aged group compared to the oldest group. Secondary ultrasound findings are valuable factors in the diagnosis of appendicitis in pediatric patients and appear to be strong predictors even in the absence of direct visualization of the appendix. For most secondary ultrasound findings, there is no statistically significant difference in the performance of age-stratified testing for pediatric appendicitis. However, the observation of an appendicolith is a more accurate predictor of appendicitis in younger patients.²²

Negative and nondiagnostic ultrasound results are problematic for clinicians. In such cases, the clinician may choose to evaluate further using abdominal computed tomography (CT) scans, repeat the ultrasound, or discharge the patient home if the clinical likelihood of acute appendicitis is low. CT scans should be considered in children with a high clinical suspicion of acute appendicitis if they have vomiting, a high white blood cell count, and an elevated serum C-reactive protein (CRP) concentration, despite negative or nondiagnostic ultrasound results.²³

Simianu et al. demonstrated high reproducibility of objective CT findings for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. Some findings, such as a large appendix diameter (>10 mm) in 76% of cases (outer wall or tip) and a fat streak in 96%, were much more frequent in cases reported as positive for appendicitis. After listing these findings using the standardized report, radiologists' certainty in diagnosing appendicitis was highly accurate and reproducible. Even so, radiologists assigned "indeterminate" diagnoses to a small number of patients. As such, next steps should focus on generating a better definition

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of which findings should be associated with this "indeterminate" category and establishing which constellation of findings can predict the likelihood of appendicitis and the success of different clinical management strategies. Ultrasound re-evaluation can be used to improve diagnostic accuracy in cases with equivocal CT features for diagnosing appendicitis. The presence of reduced compressibility and increased vascular flow in the appendiceal wall are useful ultrasound findings for differentiating appendicitis from non-appendicitis.^{24,25}

Rud B et al; reported that the accuracy of clinical assessment alone versus clinical assessment and CT were compared in three randomized controlled trials with a total of 400 participants. Two of the studies concluded that the accuracy of clinical data and CT was no superior to the accuracy of clinical assessment alone; the third study reached the opposite conclusion.²⁶

It has been confirmed that newly developed prediction scales employing three grades of striated fat, in combination with CRP or NLR (neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio) biomarkers and appendicolith or ascites features on CT, were powerful in identifying complicated acute appendicitis. On the other hand, models that do not include CT features showed limited sensitivity. These new models employ the fewest variables and, therefore, can help to quickly distinguish between complicated and uncomplicated appendicitis in clinical practice. This differentiation can help patients with uncomplicated appendicitis avoid unnecessary surgery and subsequent complications.²⁷

CT and ultrasound are practical tools in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. However, inadequate guidelines on diagnostic imaging can lead to either underutilization or overuse of these imaging modalities when acute appendicitis is suspected. Routine CT in all patients with suspected appendicitis carries the risk of ionizing radiation and contrast medium exposure, as well as delaying accurate diagnosis and treatment. Ultrasound involves non-ionizing radiation, but there is significant reported variation in its diagnostic performance. The diagnostic performance of CT and ultrasound depends on a prior assessment of the likelihood of acute appendicitis.²⁸

Computed tomography (CT) involves significant radiation exposure, and epidemiological data suggest that radiation exposure may increase the risk of developing future malignancy. This problem is of particular concern in children because they are more sensitive to the dangers of radiation, are among the most common patients presenting to the emergency department with abdominal pain, and have the highest rate of misdiagnosis. In an attempt to reduce the harmful effect of CT scans, several clinical trials are examining the diagnostic utility of lower doses of radiation, primarily in children.^{29,30}

JUSTIFICATION

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common reasons for seeking medical attention for acute abdomen and one of the

most frequent surgical emergencies in our setting. However, clinical diagnosis is sometimes difficult, which is why multiple diagnostic scales have been developed to support the treating physician's decision. The need for these scales is so great, and the constant pursuit of the most sensitive and specific one has led to the creation of numerous scales that integrate multiple evaluation factors, including signs, symptoms, biomarkers, laboratory tests, and, in some cases, imaging studies.

While various diagnostic scales exist, in much of the country most physicians continue to use the Alvarado scale, the first and oldest of these. In most comparative studies with other scales, it has been surpassed in sensitivity and specificity.

In this context, and knowing that the Alvarado scale places a large proportion of patients at a score indicating the need for imaging studies as a diagnostic definition—with computed tomography being the gold standard with excellent sensitivity and ultrasonography the first-line study—it can lead to the unnecessary use of imaging services, exposing these patients to ionizing radiation that can especially affect adolescents and children, as well as delays in diagnosis and treatment for cases of surgical emergency and the costs that these services entail.

Analyzing the management and usefulness of the Alvarado scale and its relationship to imaging studies, the treating physician can be encouraged to use scales for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis that, according to sex and age, are much more useful for decision-making that leads to a more accurate diagnosis and thus contribute to reducing and/or improving the use of the resources offered by the imaging department.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common surgical conditions worldwide, and its timely diagnosis is crucial to avoid serious complications. The Alvarado score is predominant in our country for diagnostic support in acute appendicitis, largely because it is the oldest and most practical. However, it has significant limitations, as it does not differentiate between age groups or sexes, nor does it accurately account for the progression of the disease, and it has limited criteria. Despite this, it continues to be used in our unit, making the search for safer and more effective alternatives crucial.

The preference for this scale leads to the overuse of imaging methods such as ultrasound and computed tomography as diagnostic aids, with the associated pathological and economic implications. Exposure to high doses of radiation, especially from computed tomography, is a significant risk factor for the future development of cancer, making it difficult to find a scale that adequately supports diagnosis and incorporates other diagnostic factors besides imaging. This raises important questions about the efficiency and safety of our diagnostic protocols.

Studies have demonstrated the superiority of multiple scales over the Alvarado score. Given the insistence on using this

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scale within our medical community, how many imaging studies (ultrasound or CT scans) for suspected appendicitis, guided by the Alvarado score, actually warrant it? How many of these ultrasound studies are inconclusive, leading to CT scans for diagnostic clarification, and ultimately result in negative findings?

Therefore, we conclude with the following question:

What is the usefulness of the Alvarado scale in patients with suspected acute appendicitis in relation to imaging results?

Goals

General Objective

To identify the usefulness of the Alvarado scale in patients with suspected acute appendicitis in relation to imaging results.

Specific Objectives

- Define the patient's clinical characteristics.
- Classify the imaging study (USG and CT) as positive or negative according to the Alvarado scale.
- Relate the Alvarado scale to the histopathology results of surgical specimens (appendix).
- Recognize the relationship between the results of imaging studies (USG and CT) and histopathological studies.
- Identify the sensitivity and specificity of the Alvarado scale, ultrasound, and tomography for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis.

HYPOTHESIS

Alternative Hypothesis

The Alvarado score in patients with suspected acute appendicitis is statistically significant in relation to the results of imaging studies (USG and CT)

Null Hypothesis

The Alvarado score in patients with suspected acute appendicitis is not statistically significant in relation to the results of imaging studies (USG and CT)

Definition of variables.

Variable name	Conceptual definition	Operational definition	Variable type / Measurement scale	Indicator or index
Age	Lifespan of a person from birth.	The lifespan in years was obtained from the records.	Quantitative / Ratio	Years
Sex	Organic condition that distinguishes males from females.	It was obtained from the records whether it is Male or Female according to sexual organ.	Qualitative / Nominal	Male Female

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design: A descriptive, observational, cross-sectional, retrospective study was conducted .

Study location: Emergency Department of the Regional General Hospital 1 Orizaba.

Development period: It was developed during the period from March to September 2023

Work universe: Patients with suspected acute appendicitis who were asked for imaging studies (USG and/or CT) and with histopathology results of surgical specimens at the Orizaba Regional General Hospital No. 1

Population: It was carried out with 71 patients who met the selection criteria.

Selection criteria

Inclusion:

1. Patients of all ages
2. Men and women
3. Clinical data of acute appendicitis
4. Results of diagnostic imaging studies for acute appendicitis (USG and/or CT)
5. Histopathological result of surgical specimen.

Exclusion:

1. Oncological process
2. Conservative treatment
3. Recent surgery or procedures
4. Abdominal trauma
5. Pregnant women
6. Congenital malformations
7. Steroid use in the days prior

Elimination:

1. Inconclusive imaging studies.
2. Poor image acquisition quality.
3. Incomplete file
4. Absence of histopathological study of surgical specimen

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Onset of symptoms	Date on which the first signs or indications of a disease appear.	Time elapsed from the onset of the illness until medical attention was obtained from records.	Quantitative Ratio /	Hours
Alvarado scale result	Clinical scoring system used in the diagnosis of appendicitis.	The results of clinical and laboratory assessments were obtained from records as a predictive system for the risk of acute appendicitis.	Qualitative Ordinal /	Negative 0-4 Possible 5-6 Likely 7-8 Appendicitis 9-10
Ultrasound Findings	Imaging technique findings based on the ability of tissues to reflect or refract ultrasound waves emitted by the equipment.	The results of the imaging study were obtained from the records (appendiceal wall diameter > 6 mm, peri-appendiceal fat inflammation, free abdominal fluid).	Qualitative Nominal /	Positive Negative Unfinished
Computed Tomography Findings	Findings based on the ability to obtain radiological images of a section or plane of an organ.	The result was obtained from the records. (Large diameter (>10 mm) of the appendix, fatty striations).	Qualitative Nominal /	Positive Negative Unfinished
Diagnosis in Histopathology	Findings from the examination of a tissue under a microscope.	The results of the definitive diagnostic study were obtained from the files.	Qualitative Nominal /	Acute/abscessed/incipient/simple/suppurative appendicitis/chronic periappendicitis

Overview of the study

With the authorization of the research protocol with institutional registration number R-2022-3101-98 by the Local Research Committee and the Research Ethics Committee No. 3101, the corresponding authorities of the Orizaba Regional General Hospital No. 1, Veracruz, were informed, with the collaboration of the Clinical Coordination of Education and Research in Health so that the necessary facilities could be provided to carry out the present study.

This study was based on accessing SIOC and searching for patients with a suspected diagnosis of acute appendicitis and/or requesting the records of patients who had suspected acute appendicitis from the archives for review.

Subsequently, the necessary information was collected for the study of each patient who came to request medical attention from December 1, 2017 to November 30, 2022; where the following was collected through a data collection sheet: age, sex, onset of symptoms in hours, signs and symptoms, Alvarado scale result which can be: Negative 0-4, Possible 5-6, Probable 7-8, Appendicitis 9-10; imaging study performed which can be ultrasound and/or computed tomography and the result of the same whether positive or negative, finally the

result of their histopathological examination was verified in the Pathology service as positive cases by this study method. The results were recorded on a data collection sheet and subsequently an analysis of the results obtained from the study was made and a final report for possible publication.

Sample

For this research, a finite sample size calculation formula was used for the total population of adults and children without distinction of gender, who came to the emergency service with a diagnosis of appendicitis or suspicion of acute appendicitis.

Sample Size Calculation

According to three publications with high scientific impact, which validated the detection, prevalence and prognosis of acute appendicitis in the population in the articles Comparison of the appendicitis inflammatory response and Alvarado scoring systems in the diagnosis of acute The prevalence of appendicitis in children was 0.1%; in the Demographics of Paediatric study patients presenting with acute appendicitis : A 5- year retrospective review of hospitals served by the Department of Pediatrics Surgery at the University of the In the Witwatersrand study , the prevalence of acute appendicitis in preschool children was

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found to be 2 to 9%. In the validation study by Sammalkorpi et al., the prevalence of acute appendicitis was 7% in a low-risk group according to an acute appendicitis risk scale. (Diagnosis and treatment of acute appendicitis: 2020 update of the WSES Jerusalem guidelines).

Based on the above, an average of 4.2% of the reviewed articles was obtained, and the sample size was calculated.

Where:

z^2_{α} = Coefficient given by

z : level of confidence “security” sought in Gaussian distribution

($z_{\alpha} = 0.05 = 1.96 / z_{\alpha} = 0.01 = 2.58$)

α : complementary probability to the admitted error: ($\alpha=1.962$)

p = Expected prevalence of the population,

- obtained by reviewing previous studies: (from 4.2% = 0.042)

$1-p$ = This is the difference in prevalence from unity: ($1 - 0.042 = q = 0.95$)

i = Is the statistical error, which is expected to be (5-10%): (0.05)

N = Population size?

Wanted:

n = sample size

Sample size for an infinite or unknown population:

$$n = \frac{z^2_{\alpha} p (1-p)}{Y_0^2}$$

Problem Development (statistical error 5%)

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 0.042 \times 0.95}{0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 (0.040236)}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.1545706176}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 61.82$$

Because three study groups will be analyzed, 62 patients will be required.

Data analysis and statistical aspects.

Descriptive analysis was performed using the mean, median, and standard deviation (SD) as measures of central tendency and dispersion. After verifying the normality of the groups using the Kolmogorov - Smirnov test, comparisons of means between variables with two categories were performed. Depending on the nature of the categorical variables, Fisher's

exact test was used with a significance level of <0.05 and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI). ROC curves were used to determine the sensitivity and specificity of the Alvarado scale. The statistical procedure was performed using the Statistical software. Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS Chicago, IL, USA) V. 23, and the Graph program Pad Prism version 8.0.1

Ethical aspects

The present research was conducted with the authorization of the Local Committee for Research and Ethics in Health Research No. 3101. This study adhered to international ethical standards, institutional guidelines, and the General Health Law regarding scientific experimentation on human subjects, specifically Articles 13, 16, and 20, as well as the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki, which states that the primary purpose of medical research involving human subjects is to understand the causes, evolution, and effects of diseases and to improve preventive, diagnostic, and therapeutic interventions. Since 2016, the Declaration of Helsinki has been complemented by the Taipei Declaration on ethical considerations regarding health databases and biobanks, which establishes respect for the dignity, autonomy, privacy, and confidentiality of individuals. Physicians have specific ethical and legal obligations as those responsible for protecting the information provided by their patients, and they must obtain the specific, free, and informed consent of the participants.

In this research there is no risk since no intervention will be carried out that affects the integrity and privacy of personal data since, due to the type of study, data collection will be carried out with prior authorization of an informed consent exception letter.

Nuremberg “Code” : Promulgated in 1947 and adopted by the international community, it addresses the conditions for conducting medical experiments on humans; this code expressed basic rules:

- 1.- The Subject's Consent
2. The experiment must lead to a positive result, without improvised or unnecessary means.
- 3.- There should be no unnecessary mental or physical suffering.

RESULTS

Of all patients diagnosed with acute appendicitis, the minimum age observed was 2 years, while the maximum age was 89 years, with an age range of 72 years for men and 83 years for women. In the total sample, females predominated, with a frequency of 40 patients (56.33%) and a mean age of 28.80 years, standard deviation +/- 19.36 (95% CI 22.61-34.99). Males accounted for 31 patients (43.66%) with a mean age of 28.16 years and a standard deviation +/- 17.69 (95% CI 21.67-34.65). (See Figure 1)

Figure 1. Age and sex distribution of patients

Age and sex distribution of patients, women \bar{x} 28.80 years, \pm 19.36, men \bar{x} 28.16 years, \pm 17.69 n=71

Patients were classified according to the time of symptom onset. Of the total sample, 35 (49.3%) began experiencing symptoms at 24 hours, followed by 15 patients (21.1%) at 12

hours, 11 patients (15.5%) at 72 hours, 7 patients reported symptom onset at 48 hours (9.9%), while 1 patient (1.4%) presented symptoms at 8, 36, and 96 hours, respectively. (See Graph 2)

Figure 2. Frequency of symptom onset time

The onset of symptoms within 24 hours predominated, with a frequency of 35 patients (49.3%) n=71

Patients were classified according to the Alvarado scale and the definitive imaging study, obtaining the following

Usefulness of the Alvarado Scale in Patients with Suspected Acute Appendicitis in Relation to Imaging Results

frequencies and percentages: of the patients who underwent ultrasound, the following scores on the Alvarado scale were: negative 3 (7.89%), possible 4 (10.52%), probable 22 (57%),

and appendicitis 8 (23.68%). Of those who underwent CT: negative 0, possible 3 (9.09%), probable 20 (60.6%), and appendicitis 10 (30.3%). (See Graph 3)

Figure 3. Distribution of patients on the Alvarado scale and imaging study

The diagnosis of probable appendicitis predominated in 42 patients (59.2%) according to the Alvarado scale; the most frequently used study was ultrasound in 38 patients (53.5%) n=71

were classified according to their Alvarado score and histopathology report. Of the patients diagnosed with appendicitis according to the Alvarado scale, 63.2% had

abscessed appendicitis and 41.2% had suppurative appendicitis. Of the patients diagnosed with probable appendicitis, 69% had abscessed appendicitis, 21.4% had suppurative appendicitis, and 2.8% had incipient appendicitis. A p-value of 0.340 was obtained using Fisher's exact test, indicating no statistical significance. (See Figure 4)

Figure 4. Histopathological findings classified on the Alvarado Scale

Usefulness of the Alvarado Scale in Patients with Suspected Acute Appendicitis in Relation to Imaging Results

The finding of abscessed appendicitis predominated in 63.2% of patients classified as having appendicitis by the Alvarado scale.

were classified according to the imaging study performed and the histopathological report of the appendix. Of the patients with a positive CT scan result, 22 (66.6%) had abscessed appendicitis, 1 (3%) incipient, 1 (3%) simple, and 9 (27.2%)

suppurative. Of the patients with a positive ultrasound, 26 (68.4%) had abscessed appendicitis, 1 (2.6%) incipient, 2 (5.2%) simple, 8 (21.05%) suppurative, and 1 (2.6%) chronic peri-appendicitis. All patients with negative CT and ultrasound results had abscessed appendicitis. Fisher's exact test was performed, yielding a p-value of 0.9986. (See Figure 5)

Figure 5. Histopathological report of appendix and imaging study result

Two negative results were identified, both corresponding to abscessed appendicitis, through the two imaging studies. n= 71

A receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was generated to identify the predictive utility of the Alvarado Scale in discriminating the presence of abscessed

appendicitis. The ROC curve showed an area under the curve of 0.577 with a standard error of 0.7342 and a confidence interval of 0.4340–0.7218. A score of 7 points or higher showed a sensitivity of 82.61% and a specificity of 45.08%. (See Figure 6)

Figure 6. ROC curve Alvarado scale with histopathology result

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An AUC of 0.577 was obtained with a sensitivity of 82.61% and a specified sensitivity of 45.08%.

was identified using Fisher's exact test, obtaining a p-value of 0.8791, which is considered statistically insignificant. (See Graph 7)

Figure 7. Alvarado scale and image study results

No statistical significance was found p value=0.8791 n=71 patients

The imaging studies used showed high diagnostic reliability in detecting positive cases. Ultrasound, applied to 40 patients, obtained a sensitivity of 98%, a specificity of 50%, a positive predictive value (PPV) of 97%, and a negative predictive value (NPV) of 67%.

For its part, the tomography, performed on 33 patients, showed a sensitivity of 97%, a specificity of 50%, a PPV of 97% and an NPV of 50%.

These results indicate that both imaging methods have a high capacity for correctly detecting positive cases, although their ability to identify negative cases was limited due to the low number of patients with confirmed negative results. Overall, ultrasound showed slightly superior performance in sensitivity and positive predictive value, remaining the most reliable diagnostic tool within the studied population.

	Prevalence	Sensitivity	Specificity	VPP	VPN
Ultrasound	40	98%	50%	100%	0%
Tomography	33	97%	50%	100%	0%

The imaging study that showed the best performance was ultrasound with a sensitivity of 98%.

DISCUSSION

In a 2020 study by Díaz Castro et al. on the Alvarado scale for acute appendicitis, the time from symptom onset to hospital admission ranged from 3 hours to 15 days, with an average of 44.6 hours for women and 40.22 hours for men, although the median and mode were 24 hours. A statistically significant association was found between symptom onset times greater than 36 hours and the presence of necrosis. In the present study, the results differ, as 35 patients (49.3%) of the sample began experiencing symptoms within 24 hours, followed by 15 patients (21.1%) who began experiencing acute symptoms within 12 hours, with a mean of 32.23 hours and a standard deviation of 21.48 hours.

In that study, they also identified that the mean score recorded with the Alvarado scale was 5.8 (SD=1.86), 5.77 in women and 5.82 in men (p=0.86). These results contrast with those of the present study, which showed a mean score of 7.37 (SD=1.75) using the Alvarado scale. By age group, the mean score on the Alvarado scale was highest in the 5-14 year age group (6.19; SD=1.56). In the present study, the mean score on the Alvarado scale was highest in the 26-64 year age group.

Pifeleti et al. conducted a study on the usefulness of the Alvarado score, comparing it with histopathology results. They reported that sensitivity and specificity were 91.97% and 50%, respectively, with an Alvarado score ≥ 5 , and 63.5%

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and 75%, respectively, with an Alvarado score ≥ 7 . Furthermore, Nascimento et al. demonstrated a sensitivity of 88.17% and a specificity of 37.5% for an Alvarado score ≥ 5 , and a sensitivity of 38.71%, a specificity of 87.5%, a positive predictive value (PPV) of 97.3%, and a negative predictive value (NPV) of 10.94% for an Alvarado score ≥ 7 . It was noted that with an increasing cutoff point, sensitivity decreased, but specificity increased. Our research yielded similar results, as the Alvarado scale with a cutoff point ≥ 5 showed a sensitivity of 62.86% and a specificity of 16.67%, while with a cutoff point ≥ 7 it showed a sensitivity of 82.61% and a specificity of 45.83%. These results are similar to previous research, suggesting that the Alvarado score was not a useful method for diagnosing acute appendicitis.

Additionally, Khan et al. (2022) conducted a prospective study in Pakistan with 200 patients presenting to the emergency department with suspected acute appendicitis. They evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of the Alvarado score by comparing it with intraoperative findings and reported that, for a cutoff score ≥ 7 , sensitivity was 78.9% and specificity was 65.2%, while for a cutoff score ≥ 5 , sensitivity increased to 92.4% but specificity decreased to 42.8%. These findings are consistent with the trend observed in our study, where a lower cutoff score increases sensitivity but reduces specificity, again demonstrating that, while the Alvarado score is useful as an initial diagnostic tool, it has limitations in definitively differentiating cases of appendicitis when used in isolation.

Atema and colleagues developed two scoring systems for predicting complicated or uncomplicated acute appendicitis, combining clinical and radiological characteristics: one using ultrasound features and the other using CT. The ultrasound system achieved a sensitivity of 96.6% and a specificity of 45.7%; for CT, the sensitivity and specificity were 90.2% and 70.3%, respectively. In the present study, it was not possible to compare the sensitivity and specificity of the imaging studies because all 71 patients in the sample experienced some phase of acute appendicitis, and therefore there were no negative results.

The results of this study show that the Alvarado score had an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.7342, indicating moderate diagnostic accuracy for predicting acute appendicitis. This finding is consistent with reports in the literature. For example, a meta-analysis by Ohle et al. (2011) found that the Alvarado score has an overall sensitivity of 82% and a specificity of 81% for appendicitis, although its diagnostic performance improves when applied to men and in selected clinical settings.

A study by Mostbeck et al. (2016) reported that ultrasound has an average sensitivity of 78–83% and a specificity of 83–88% for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. However, in this study, ultrasound demonstrated a sensitivity of 98%, which is significantly higher, suggesting that, in the present study, the diagnostic performance of ultrasound may have been

optimized by the operator's experience or by appropriate patient selection.

Regarding computed tomography, a meta-analysis by Doria et al. (2006) concluded that CT has a sensitivity of 94% and a specificity of 95% for appendicitis, making it the gold standard in many hospitals, especially in adults. Our research reported a sensitivity of 97%, which is consistent with international studies.

Comparing these findings, it is worth noting that while the Alvarado score offers a useful, quick, and inexpensive tool for initial risk stratification, its diagnostic accuracy is lower compared to imaging methods. However, its usefulness increases when employed as a screening tool to determine the need for more expensive or invasive studies. As suggested by Kularatna et al. (2017), combining the Alvarado score with ultrasound can increase diagnostic accuracy and reduce the need for CT scans, especially in pediatric populations or young women, where radiation exposure should be minimized.

Given the variability in the diagnostic accuracy of the Alvarado scale, several authors have proposed more effective alternatives. For example, the RIPASA Scale (Raja Isteri) Pengiran Anak Saleha The Appendicitis Score has shown promising results in Asian and Latin American populations. A recent meta-analysis by Chong et al. (2021) reported that the RIPASA scale has an average sensitivity of 94.0% and a specificity of 72.3%, consistently outperforming the Alvarado scale in settings with a high prevalence of atypical appendicitis. Similarly, scales such as the AIR Score (Appendicitis Inflammatory Response Scores (IRS) have demonstrated greater accuracy, especially when inflammatory biomarkers such as C-reactive protein and neutrophil count are integrated. These findings suggest the need to consider combined tools that integrate clinical, laboratory, and imaging parameters to optimize diagnostic accuracy and reduce negative laparotomies.

CONCLUSION

In the present investigation: "Usefulness of the Alvarado scale in patients with suspected acute appendicitis in relation to imaging results" the alternative hypothesis is rejected, which states that the Alvarado scale in patients with suspected acute appendicitis is statistically significant in relation to the results of imaging studies (USG and CT) since when rated using ROC curves it showed a low AUC performance 0.577, a sensitivity of 82.61%, and a specified value of 45.08%, respectively. This research is consistent with other studies conducted in Latin America on the usefulness of the Alvarado scale versus imaging studies.

The Alvarado score has proven to be a useful, simple, non-invasive, and rapid tool for guiding the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. However, due to its low specificity, the use of imaging studies to confirm the diagnosis is always recommended, as is the use of scales such as RIPASA or AIR Score, which have demonstrated greater sensitivity and

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specificity and integrate clinical, laboratory, and imaging parameters to optimize diagnostic accuracy and reduce unnecessary interventions.

In the present study, the female gender predominated in patients diagnosed with acute appendicitis and the most frequent age group was 26 to 64 years followed by the 6-13 year group, it should be noted that most of the patients presented a histopathology report of abscessed appendicitis. The use of scales for the suspicion of acute appendicitis, such as the Alvarado scale, is and will always be very useful in the approach to abdominal pain. This research will contribute to the medical community's greater knowledge about the clinical characteristics identified in patients and the effectiveness of both the predictive scale and the imaging studies evaluated.

This study opens a window of opportunity for future research to describe and contrast tomographic and ultrasonographic findings and correlate them with clinical presentation and time of evolution.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

To Marcus Mijangos Pinkus. The love of my life. "I want you to know, my son, that leaving you was so painful, and it will only be worth it to give you the life you deserve. It is the only thing that matters to me."

To Lidia Cardona Castellanos, Luisa Hepsiva Mijangos Cardona and Rebeca Santos Mijangos. My Family.

To Isis Zamudio Vázquez. The most precious jewel in Orizaba, Veracruz.

"How long is forever? – Sometimes, just a second."

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Annexes .

Annex I. Informed Consent Exception Letter

**GOBIERNO DE
MÉXICO**

Fecha: a 01 de Diciembre de 2022

SOLICITUD DE EXCEPCION DE LA CARTA DE CONSENTIMIENTO INFORMADO

Para cumplimiento a las disposiciones legales nacionales en materia de investigación en salud, solicito al Comité de Ética en Investigación del Hospital General Regional 1 Orizaba que apruebe la excepción de la carta de consentimiento informado debido a que el protocolo de investigación "Utilidad de la escala de Alvarado en pacientes con sospecha de Apendicitis Aguda en relación a resultados de imagenología", es una propuesta de investigación sin riesgo que implica la recolección de los siguientes datos ya contenidos en los expedientes clínicos:

- | | | | |
|----|---------------------------------|----|---------------------------------|
| a) | Nombre | e) | Resultado de Escala de Alvarado |
| b) | Edad | f) | Hallazgos Ultrasonográficos |
| c) | Genero | g) | Hallazgos Tomográficos |
| d) | Tiempo de evolución de síntomas | h) | Resultados de Histopatología |

MANIFIESTO DE CONFIDENCIALIDAD Y PROTECCION DE DATOS

En apego a las disposiciones legales de protección de datos personales, me comprometo a recopilar solo la información que sea necesaria para la investigación y esté contenida en el expediente clínico y/o base de datos disponible, así como codificarla para imposibilitar la identificación del paciente, resguardarla, mantener la confidencialidad de esta y no hacer mal uso o compartirla con personas ajenas a este protocolo.

La información recabada será utilizada exclusivamente para la realización del protocolo "Utilidad de la escala de Alvarado en pacientes con sospecha de Apendicitis Aguda en relación a resultados de imagenología" cuyo propósito es producto de tesis.

Estando en conocimiento de que en caso de no dar cumplimiento se procederá acorde a las sanciones que procedan de conformidad con lo dispuesto en las disposiciones legales en materia de investigación en salud, vigentes y aplicables.

Atentamente

Nombre: Mario German Montes Osorio

Categoría contractual: Coordinador de Planeación y Enlace Institucional D3 y D4

Investigador Responsable

2022 Flores
Año de Magón
PRECURSOR DE LA REVOLUCIÓN MEXICANA

Usefulness of the Alvarado Scale in Patients with Suspected Acute Appendicitis in Relation to Imaging Results

Annex II. Data Collection Instrument:

Data collection instrument.

“Usefulness of the Alvarado scale in patients with suspected of acute appendicitis in relation to imaging results”

Place of investigation: Regional General Hospital 1 Orizaba, Veracruz.

Instructions: Fill out with a pen, underline, mark with an “x” or complete as appropriate.

Folio: _____ Affiliation: _____

Patient's name: _____

Personal background:

1. Age: _____ years
2. Gender: ___ Male ___ Female

Clinical manifestations

3. Onset of symptoms: _____ hours
4. Alvarado Scale Result: ___ 0 - 4 ___ 5 - 6 ___ 7 - 8 ___ 9 - 10

Image conclusion

5. Ultrasound: ___ Positive ___ Negative ___ Inconclusive
6. Tomography: ___ Positive ___ Negative ___ Inconclusive

Pathology Result

7. Sample Result: ___ Appendicitis _____
___ Appendix without alterations ___ Incomplete

Additional observations: _____

Criterios de evaluación de la escala diagnóstica de Alvarado	
Criterio	Valor
Dolor en cuadrante inferior derecho	2
Signo de Blumberg positivo	1
Migración del dolor	1
Nausea o vómito	1
Anorexia	1
Temperatura oral superior a 37.2 °C	1
Recuento de leucocitos mayor de 10 000 por mm ³	2
Neutrofilia mayor a 70%	1
Decisión	Puntaje
<i>Criterios de decisión de la escala diagnóstica de Alvarado</i>	
Negativo para apendicitis	0-4
Posible apendicitis	5-6
Probable apendicitis	7-8
Apendicitis	9-10

Annex IV. Alvarado Scale (Sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV).

Screening performance characteristics of different scoring systems in prediction of acute appendicitis in emergency department

	Alvarado	Ohmann	RIPASA	Tzanakis	Eskelinen
TP	40	47	55	56	42
TN	8	8	8	8	7
FP	1	1	1	1	2
FN	25	18	10	9	23
Sensitivity	60.9 (48.64-73.35)	71.9 (59.81-82.69)	75 (64.81-86.47)	84.4 (75.34-93.47)	64.1 (51.77-76.08)
Specificity	89.9 (51.75-99.72)	89.9 (51.75-99.72)	99.72 (51.75-100)	99.88 (51.75-99.72)	78 (39.99-99.19)
PPV	97.56 (86.19-99.61)	97.92 (88.04-99.67)	98.04 (88.69-99.69)	98.25 (89.80-99.72)	95.45 (85.93-98.63)
NPV	24.24 (17.89-31.98)	30.77 (21.98-41.21)	34.78 (24.44-46.80)	47.06 (31.72-62.97)	23.33 (15.86-32.96)
PLR	5.54 (0.86-35.56)	6.51 (1.02-41.55)	6.92 (1.09-44.15)	7.75 (1.22-49.24)	2.91 (0.85-10.00)
NLR	0.43 (0.29-0.64)	0.21 (0.20-0.49)	0.26 (0.16-0.43)	0.16 (0.08-0.30)	0.45 (0.28-0.73)
AUC	0.93 (0.87-0.99)	0.94 (0.88-1.00)	0.89 (0.81-0.97)	0.96 (0.90-1.00)	0.86 (0.77-0.97)

Data are presented with 95% confidence interval (CI). Measures are calculated in cut-offs: ≥ 8 for Alvarado score; ≥ 12 for Ohmann score; ≥ 12 for RIPASA score; ≥ 8 for Tzanakis score; ≥ 57 for Eskelinen score.

Annex V. Ultrasound diagnostic criteria for acute appendicitis

Ultrasound diagnostic criteria for acute appendicitisAperistaltic, non-compressible, dilated appendix (>6 mm in outer diameter)

Usefulness of the Alvarado Scale in Patients with Suspected Acute Appendicitis in Relation to Imaging Results

Hyperechoic appendicolith with posterior acoustic shadowing

Different layers of the appendicular wall

Prominent echogenic pericecal and periappendiceal fat

Hyperechoic periappendiceal structure: amorphous (~ or >10 mm) seen surrounding a non-compressible appendix with a diameter >6 mm

Periappendiceal fluid collection

Target appearance (axial section)

Periappendiceal reactive lymph node prominence/enlargement

Wall thickening (3 mm or more)

Alteration of the mural spectral Doppler

Annex VI . Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value in ultrasonographic findings. (21)

Sensitivity and specificity values of sonographic findings for acute complicated appendicitis

Sonographic finding	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
Appendiceal wall diameter				
>5 mm	99.4 (97.4,99.9)	2.1 (1.2,3.5)	34.6 (34.3,34.9)	87.5 (61.5,96.8)
>6 mm	98.0 (95.9,99.2)	11.4 (9.1,14.0)	36.5 (25.8,37.2)	91.6 (83.5,95.9)
>7 mm	94.5 (91.6,96.7)	25.7 (22.4,29.2)	39.8 (38.6,41.1)	90.1 (85.2,93.5)
>8 mm	81.9 (77.4,85.8)	43.9 (40.1,47.8)	43.2 (41.2,45.2)	82.4 (78.6,85.6)
>9 mm	68.1 (62.9,73.0)	58.1 (54.3,61.9)	45.8 (43.0,48.7)	77.8 (74.8,80.5)
Appendiceal wall oedema	7.5 (4.9,10.8)	92.8 (90.6,94.7)	35.1 (25.5,46.2)	65.9 (65.0,66.7)
Periappendiceal fat inflammation	57.8 (52.4;63.0)	62.5 (58.5,66.1)	44.5 (41.2,47.8)	74.0 (71.3,76.5)
Free abdominal fluid	46.3 (40.9,51.7)	61.4 (57.6,65.1)	38.4 (35.0,42.0)	68.7 (66.2,71.1)
Abscess	4.0 (2.2,6.7)	99.7 (98.9,100)	87.5 (61.5,96.8)	66.6 (66.1,67.1)
Conglomerate	2.6 (1.2,4.9)	99.9 (99.2,100)	90.0 (53.4,98.6)	66.3 (66.0,66.7)
Appendicolith	20.1 (16.0,24.7)	90.3 (87.8,92.4)	51.9 (44.1,59.5)	68.5 (67.2,69.7)
Lymphadenitis	15.2 (11.6,19.4)	83.3 (80.2,86.0)	32.1 (26.0,39.0)	65.3 (64.1,66.6)
Expected perforation	31.9 (27.0,37.1)	94.9 (93.9,96.5)	76.6 (69.5,82.4)	72.8 (71.3,74.3)

NPV, negative predictive value; PPV, positive predictive value.

Data in parentheses are the 95% confidence interval.

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Annex VII. Computed tomography diagnostic criteria for acute appendicitis

Diagnostic criteria in tomography for acute appendicitis

Appendiceal dilation (> 6 mm outer diameter)

Wall thickening (> 3 mm) and enhancement

Thickening of the cecal apex: cecal bar sign, arrowhead sign

Intraluminal fluid depth >2.6 mm in a dilated appendix (>6 mm) without periappendiceal inflammation

Periappendiceal inflammation

Fatty striations

Thickening of the lateroconal fascia or mesoappendix

Extraluminal fluid

Phlegmon (inflammatory mass)

Abscess

No focal wall enhancement representing necrosis (gangrenous appendicitis) and a precursor to perforation

Annex VIII . Use of images and performance, stratified by sex and risk category. (AUC , sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV)

Use of imaging and performance, stratified by sex and risk category				
	Women		Men	
	Low risk (AAS ≤ 8) (n = 1856)	High risk (AAS > 8) (n = 1577)	Low risk (AIRS ≤ 2) (n = 209)	High risk (AIRS > 2) (n = 1418)
Ultrasound imaging	1291 (69.6)	916 (58.1)	59 (28.2)	205 (14.5)
AUC*	0.63 (0.57, 0.70)	0.68 (0.65, 0.71)	1.00 (n.a.)	0.66 (0.60, 0.72)
Sensitivity	0.28	0.38	1.00	0.37
Specificity	0.99	0.98	1.00	0.95
NPV	0.97	0.82	1.00	0.74
PPV	0.54	0.84	1.00	0.79
CT	208 (11.2)	316 (20.0)	41 (19.6)	341 (24.0)
AUC*	0.99 (0.98, 1.00)	0.93 (0.90, 0.96)	1.00 (n.a.)	0.92 (0.90, 0.95)
Sensitivity	1.00	0.92	1.00	0.94
Specificity	0.97	0.95	1.00	0.91
NPV	1.00	0.96	1.00	0.94
PPV	0.62	0.91	1.00	0.90
No imaging	434 (23.4)	456 (28.9)	111 (53.1)	910 (64.2)

Values in parentheses are percentages unless indicate otherwise; *values in parentheses are 95 per cent confidence intervals. AAS, Adult Appendicitis Score; AIRS, Appendicitis Inflammatory Response Score; AUC, area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve; n.a., not applicable; NPV, negative predictive value; PPV, positive predictive value.